

Structural Investigations of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of Phenylazobenzoylacetone

S. B. KHATAVKAR*, G. S. SADANA and A. A. DESHMUKH

Department of Chemistry, G. N. Khalsa College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 14 April 1986, revised 11 April 1988, accepted 1 June 1988

Complexes of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) of phenylazobenzoylacetone (PABA) have been isolated in solid state and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic, uv-visible and ir spectral data. Physicochemical data provide evidences for the existence of octahedral $\text{Cu}(\text{HR})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{HR})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{HR})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{HR})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Co}(\text{HR})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{HR})_2(\text{Ac})_2$ complexes, square-planar dimeric $(\text{Cu}-\text{R}(\text{Ac}))_2$ complex and spin-free square-planar $\text{NiHR}(\text{Ac})$ complex, where HR is ligand PABA.

THE chemistry of aryldiazonato complexes is of recent origin. These complexes display much of the expected structural similarity with isoelectronic nitrosyl complexes¹. King and Bisnette² first synthesised molybdenum complexes by displacing carbonyl group in $\text{Mo}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2(\text{CO})_3$ by the aryldiazonion ion, while the aryldiazonato complexes were reviewed by Gaughan *et al.*³. Various modes of formulations were proposed for the formation of diazonium complexes⁴. Bayer and Claisen⁵ prepared phenylazobenzoylacetone and phenylazobenzoylacetone while Kluber and Lewis⁶ prepared their metal complexes. Talati and Kapadia⁷ prepared only copper(II) complexes, but detailed study pertaining to the preparation and assignment of structures to these diazo complexes in the presence of different anion moiety has not been reported so far.

A critical survey of literature showed that the preparation of metal complexes of phenylazobenzoylacetone (abbreviated as PABA) have not been carried out. Present paper deals with the preparation and structural investigations of metal complexes of the reagent PABA with perchlorate, nitrate salts of copper(II) and chlorides and acetates of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II). The metal complexes have been isolated in pure solid state and characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic and spectral data.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade, otherwise L.R. grade chemicals were purified by standard methods⁸ before use. Solutions of 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate and 0.01 M sodium tetraborate were used as standard buffer solutions for pH 4.01 and 9.18, respectively, at room temperature to calibrate the pH-meter (Elico). For conductivity measurements a Toshniwal magic-eye conductivity bridge was used.

Spectral measurements were carried out on a CZ-VSU 2P spectrophotometer. Spectrophotometric calibrations were confirmed by 40 ppm potassium chromate (A.R.) prepared in 0.05 M potassium hydroxide solution for ultraviolet region (λ_{max} 256 and 365 nm) and for visible region 2200 ppm cobalt chloride prepared in 0.05 M hydrochloric acid was used (λ_{max} 509 nm). For the measurements of diffuse reflectance spectra of solid complexes, a CZ-VSU 2P spectrophotometer with reflectance attachment was used with standard magnesium oxide block as a blank (supplied along with instrument). Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. The magnetic measurements were carried out on a VEB-ANALYTIC modified balance (0.00001 g FSR) incorporated with powerful electromagnets and variable DC supply, designed and developed by I.I.T., Powai, Bombay.

The reagent phenylazobenzoylacetone (abbreviated as PABA) was prepared mainly according to the procedure described in the literature⁵.

Preparation of solid chelates: Solid metal chelates were synthesised by refluxing a mixture of metal salt (50 ml, 0.01 M) in 75% ethanol and PABA (50 ml, 0.02 M) in 75% ethanol after raising the pH to the appropriate value (Table 1), for 2–3 h. On cooling the mixture, the resulting coloured precipitate was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried around 80°. All the metal chelates were synthesised by this method. In the case of copper(II) acetate and nickel(II) acetate chelates, metal and ligand were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

Results and Discussion

The solid metal chelates do not possess sharp melting point and decompose on at 260–300°. These compounds were analysed for C, H, N and metal (Table 1). From these data it is evident that the metal chelates possess 1 : 2 (M : R) stoichiometry except in the case of chelates formed by

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Metal salt	Mol. formula of compd.	Mol. weight	pH of formation	μ_{eff}^*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
						O	H	N	Metal
1.	Reagent PABA	$C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2$	266.0	—	—	71.86 (72.18)	6.02 (5.88)	10.92 (10.52)	—
2.	Copper(II) chloride	$Cu(HR)_2Cl.H_2O$	648.05	4.1	1.92	49.81 (50.12)	4.33 (4.17)	7.23 (7.30)	9.56 (9.79)
3.	Copper(II) perchlorate	$Cu(HR)_2(ClO_4)_2$	794.55	3.9	1.74	35.60 (36.40)	3.01 (2.88)	5.44 (5.30)	8.42 (8.01)
4.	Copper(II) nitrate	$Cu(HR)_2(NO_3)_2$	719.55	4.6	1.79	41.68 (42.42)	3.10 (2.87)	12.24 (12.38)	9.08 (8.85)
5.	Copper(II) acetate	$Cu.R.CH_3COO$	387.55	4.9	Diamag.	54.88 (55.73)	4.61 (4.13)	7.38 (7.23)	16.71 (16.4)
6.	Nickel(II) chloride	$Ni(HR)_2Cl_2$	661.69	4.5	2.79	48.08 (48.64)	3.88 (3.29)	7.12 (7.69)	9.05 (8.89)
7.	Nickel(II) acetate	$Ni(HR)(CH_3COO)_2$	442.69	7.5	Diamag.	53.68 (54.33)	4.91 (4.80)	6.62 (6.33)	13.44 (13.29)
8.	Cobalt(II) chloride	$Co(HR)_2Cl.H_2O$	643.43	7.3	5.1	49.81 (50.86)	4.18 (3.97)	7.88 (7.42)	9.35 (9.17)
9.	Cobalt(II) acetate	$Co(HR)_2(CH_3COO)_2$	708.93	7.5	5.2	53.94 (54.30)	4.86 (4.34)	7.06 (6.72)	8.48 (8.38)

*At 303 K.

copper(II) acetate and nickel(II) acetate which possess 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

The solid metal chelates formed by copper(II) acetate and nickel(II) acetate are diamagnetic and the rest of the chelates are paramagnetic. Molecular formulae assigned to these metal chelates indicate that these could be broadly classified into four categories : (i) MRX (e.g., $Cu.R.CH_3COO$), (ii) $M.HR.X_2$ (e.g., $Ni.HR.(CH_3COO)_2$), (iii) $M.HR_2.X.H_2O$ (e.g., $Cu.HR_2.Cl.H_2O$, $Co.HR_2.Cl.H_2O$), and (iv) $M.(HR)_2.X_2$ (e.g., $Cu(HR)_2(ClO_4)_2$, $Cu(HR)_2(NO_3)_2$, $Ni(HR)_2Cl_2$ and $Co(HR)_2(CH_3COO)_2$) where HR stands for the reagent PABA, M stands for the metal ion and X for the respective anion. All these metal complexes were found insoluble in water and most common organic solvents and hence the complexes could not be crystallised.

Three paramagnetic copper(II) complexes exhibit magnetic moment around 1.78 B.M. (303 K) indicating them to be octahedral or distorted octahedral⁹ while metal chelates formed by copper(II) and nickel(II) acetates are diamagnetic, indicating the copper(II) complex to be a spin-paired and polymeric; probably dimeric square-planar complex, suggesting copper-copper interaction¹⁰ in polymeric solid state. Diamagnetic nature of the copper(II) complex also indicates its antiferromagnetic nature¹¹ involving super-exchange phenomena with oxygen of acetate group bridging copper ions¹². Orange-red color of nickel(II) acetate chelate and its diamagnetic character are indicative of its square-planar stereochemistry¹³. Metal chelates formed by nickel(II) chloride, cobalt(II) chloride and cobalt(II) acetate are paramagnetic. The observed values (5.1 B.M. at 303 K) of the magnetic moments of these metal chelates suggests them to be octahedral¹⁴.

Diffuse reflectance spectra : As the metal chelates were insoluble in common organic solvents it was

not possible to record their electronic spectra. Diffuse reflectance spectra of the three paramagnetic copper(II) complexes show a broad diffuse reflectance band around 810 nm, which may be due to the transition ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ suggesting octahedral stereochemistry¹⁵ for the three copper(II) chelates, while the diamagnetic copper(II) complex exhibits two bands at 390 and 710 nm and their ratio of the optical densities is nearly 2, a characteristic feature generally exhibited by dimeric square-planar copper(II) complexes¹⁶. Diffuse reflectance spectra of the orange-red diamagnetic nickel(II) chelate exhibit two bands at 470 and 590 nm, indicating square-planar stereochemistry¹⁷.

Diffuse reflectance spectra of the two cobalt(II) chelates consist of two bands around 1250 and 575 nm which can be assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$, respectively¹⁸. These bands suggest octahedral stereochemistry for the two cobalt chelates in conformity with the conclusions arrived from the magnetic properties. The diffuse reflectance spectra for the paramagnetic nickel(II) chelate obtained from nickel(II) chloride showed two bands around 705 and 400 nm assignable to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. These bands suggest octahedral stereochemistry for nickel(II) ions¹⁹.

Infrared spectra of the reagent PABA do not show any band assignable to OH while sharp and strong bands around 3450 cm^{-1} in the two copper(II) and cobalt(II) chloride chelates indicate the presence of coordinated water molecule in these complexes²⁰. Infrared spectra of the reagent PABA show bands at 1418 and 1207 cm^{-1} assignable to the primary and secondary frequencies of N=N respectively²¹, which are found to have shifted to lower frequency side on complexation, indicating the participation of azo nitrogen in coordination, in each of the complexes except in the case of

diamagnetic copper(II) acetate complex where azo group does not participate in complex formation. Infrared spectra of the reagent does not show any band in the region 400–600 cm^{-1} while in the spectra of all the metal chelates two new bands in the range 400–600 cm^{-1} are found suggesting the formation of M–N and M–O bonding^{2,3} in the said complexes except in the cases of dimeric copper(II) acetate chelate only, which does not show any band for M–N. The binuclear copper(II) chelate requires the presence of bands due to bonded acetate group and metal–oxygen. Bands at 1 603 and 1 341 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the complex (Cu R.Ac)₂ are allotted to bonded acetate group^{2,3} to the metal ion forming oxygen bridge between metal ions in the dimeric copper(II) complex, while the band observed at 555 cm^{-1} in the complex, found absent in the spectra of the ligand PABA, is attributed to metal–oxygen vibrations^{2,4}.

In view of the experimental evidences the paramagnetic copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chelates may be assigned octahedral stereochemistry whereas the diamagnetic copper(II) acetate chelate and orange-red nickel(II) acetate chelate are spin-free square-planar complexes.

References

1. A. CHAKRAVARTY and K. C. KALIA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2016.
2. R. B. KING and M. B. BISNETTE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 5694; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 800.
3. A. P. GAUGHAN, B. L. HAYMORE, J. A. IBERS, W. H. MYERS, T. E. NAPPIER and W. W. MEAK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 6859.
4. N. C. CONNELLY and J. D. DAVIS, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1975, **38**, 385; J. A. IBERS and B. L. HAYMORE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1869; G. N. SCHRAUZER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 1891; J. C. CLARK and R. C. CREEKSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 686; B. CARROL and J. C. LALORE, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, **37**, 54; A. NOSMEYANOV, Y. A. CHAPOVSKII and L. G. MAKAROVA, *Inv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1965, 1310, F. J. L. OASHMAN, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1970, **29**, 24, 1971, **32**, 351.
5. O. BAYER and L. OLAISEN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 1697.
6. KLUBER and LEWIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **82**, 5777.
7. A. M. TALATI and R. N. KAPADIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 767.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1975, A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1975, p. 865.
9. J. FERGUSON, R. L. BELFORD and T. S. PIPER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **37**, 1569.
10. J. LEWIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 6464; L. DUBICKI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 93.
11. J. B. BRACON and R. J. PHILLIPS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 227.
12. T. MUTTO, M. KATO and J. IMAI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 5, 1539; B. N. FIGGIS and D. J. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 2175.
13. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
14. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 2nd ed., Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 870.
15. Ref. 14, p. 901.
16. C. FUTANI and P. O. TOLLA, *Gazz Chim. Ital.*, 1960, **90**, 280; K. C. KALIA and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 2231; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **7**, 1531; R. L. MARTIN and H. WATERMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2545, 1959, 1359.
17. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
18. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectra", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
19. Ref. 14, p. 882.
20. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
21. L. I. BELLAMBY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1958, M. J. MORGAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2151.
22. V. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 213.
23. V. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2409.
24. R. J. NIEDZIELSKI and G. ZNIDER, 1965, 43, 2618; J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1971.